

Review Article

Vaccine efficacy in mutant SARS-CoV-2 variants

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ABSTRACT

Many aspects of the SARS-CoV-2 virus remain poorly understood, including its rapid mutation and its effects on populations of different ages. The present literature of review is focused on the effectiveness of current available vaccines in view of emerging several SARS-CoV-2 variants. The most dangerous and infectious SARS-CoV-2 strain, B117, was recently discovered in the United Kingdom, and another new variant, 501.V2, was discovered in South Africa. In countries such as the United States, Japan, India, and Brazil, the variant B117 spread far more quickly than the original strain. The new SARS-CoV-2 mutations have made producing a universal and effective vaccine more difficult. SARS-CoV-2's S protein, which aids in receptor identification and membrane fusion, is a primary target for vaccine development using its mRNA or inactivated virus. Currently, in the interval of few days new more infectious SARS-CoV-2 mutant is detected, started from SARS-CoV-2 Alpha (B.1.1.7), beta (B.1.351), delta (B.1.617.2), delta plus, gamma (P.1) and now variant lambda. The variant detected first in Peru and spread almost 27 countries including UK that accounts for 82% of new infections. These mutant variants are posing new challenge even to the fully vaccinated individuals and a challenge for the public health. Thus, a need to review current treatment vaccination guideline and strategy as early as possible. Reporting all new SARS-CoV-2 variants and their effectiveness in response to several available vaccines, we would like to draw the attention of health care provider, and all developed countries health care agencies including WHO to frame new guidelines for vaccination and immediate intervention to control the development of new SARS-CoV-2 variants from the third world countries by providing vaccines to the poor countries as early as possible.

Keywords: B117; COVID-19; mutations; SARS-CoV-2; therapies; Vaccines.

Introduction

In December 2019, SARS-CoV-2 emerged in Wuhan, China ¹ and spread to various nations around the world (Figure 1). A new SARS-CoV-2 strain, B117, was first observed in southeastern England in September 2020. It forced another round of tight lockdowns as patients overwhelmed hospitals in these regions and has since spread to the United States, France, Brazil, Canada, and India (Figure 2). Experts are concerned that mutation will hinder ongoing immunization efforts. As a result of the mutant SARS-CoV-2 strain discovered in the United Kingdom, more than 80 countries closed their borders to the island nation. Travelers from that country will be required to show a negative COVID-19 test before boarding flights to most of the countries in the World. Worldwide, nearly 4,031,709 people have died in the pandemic. With the emergence of this new strain, the number of cases among children has risen; however, there is no conclusive evidence that the novel SARS-CoV-2 variant has a unique propensity to infect or cause sickness in younger patients.

The new SARS-CoV-2 strain includes significant gene alterations in its spike (S) protein that make it easier for the virus to spread from person to person: The B117 mutant strain is approximately 50% more contagious than

Figure 1. SARS-Cov2 mediated COVID-19 infection across the globe as of July 31st, 2021

earlier variants. Scientists are concerned that this new strain could result in a significant increase in the number of cases and deaths. These surges will occur at a time when many hospitals are already overburdened, causing fatality rates to skyrocket as patients who may otherwise

have survived succumb to a lack of resources such as staff, equipment, and beds. According to the US CDC's models, the new B117 strain of SARS-CoV-2 in the UK and 501.V2 in South Africa may resurface in late April any viral infection. Because DCs are prevalent in the respiratory tract and respond to inflammation, they have been identified as a potential candidate in antigen presentation during SARS infection and in understanding the immunopathology of SARS¹¹.

Figure 2. SARS-Cov2 (B117) variant infections spread in various countries of the globe.

To cause coronavirus infection, innate immune cells produce an effective antiviral response by viral infection receptors known as pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), which recognize pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). C-type lectin-like receptors, Toll-like receptors (TLR), NOD-like receptors (NLR), RIG-I-like receptors (RLR), and cytoplasmic free-molecule receptors such as cGAS-STING, IFI16, and others are examples of PRRs¹². Endosomal RNA receptors TLR3 and TLR7, as well as the cytosolic RNA sensor RIG-I/MDA5, identify RNA viruses like coronavirus, viral genomic RNA, or replication intermediates like double-stranded RNA (dsRNA). This identification activates many signaling pathways, causing inflammation and the development of a cellular immune response. Interferon regulatory factor 3 (IRF3), nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B), and AP-1 are all transcription factors activated by these pathways. As a result, these factors encourage the synthesis of interferons of type I (IFN-I), inflammatory cytokines, and chemokines¹³. In SARS patients, a cytokine storm is known to occur because of an immune system overreaction. The use of recombinant IFN-I and IFN-II as antiviral cytokines that limit viral replication in targeted cells is one treatment for this condition. Cyclosporine-targeting medicines like cyclosporine A and alisporivir are two further options for controlling host immune response in COVID infection. Through cyclophilin A and cyclophilin B, the CD147 receptor modulates cytokine production and chemotaxis in inflammatory cells¹⁴. B cells, with the help of T cells, develop into plasma cells after being influenced by virus immune responses to mediate antibody production. Plasma cells subsequently create antibodies specific to a viral antigen. Neutralizing antibodies are effective in inhibiting the virus from entering host cells and limiting infection, and they play

a critical protective role later in infection, preventing relapse. Infected cells, on the other hand, show a cellular immune response, which is mediated by T-lymphocytes. Helper T cells oversee the entire adaptive immune response, while cytotoxic T cells are essential for the clearing and cleansing of virally infected cells. Lung epithelial cells, alveolar macrophages, and neutrophils initiate the innate immune response. Adaptive immune responses involving T and B cells are triggered in the next stage to complete the immune response. When it comes to viral infections, the innate immune system is the first line of defense. When a virus infects a cell, it produces and secretes interferon (IFN) molecules. IFN- α and IFN- β operate as signaling molecules, activating an antiviral response in surrounding cells and rendering them immune to infection¹⁵. SARS coronavirus (SARS-CoV), which is comparable to SARS-CoV-2, has been shown to decrease antiviral type I interferon induction¹⁶.

Beyond ACE 2, integrins as potential receptors for SARS-CoV-2 entrance

Integrins are a family of cell surface receptors, formed through an on covalent association of two type transmembrane glycoproteins, the 18 α and 8 β subunits, which combine to form at least 24 different heterodimers to mediate the attachment of cells to the extracellular matrix as well to other cells. Integrins are widely Integrins are a group of cell surface receptors that are created by the noncovalent connection of two type I transmembrane glycoproteins, the 18 and 8 subunits, which combine to form at least 24 distinct heterodimers to mediate cell attachment to the extracellular matrix and to other cells. Integrins are found all over the body, and each nucleated cell has its own integrin signature. Integrins are a heterodimeric family of cell surface receptors that connect extracellular matrix proteins to the cytoskeleton within the cell. They have a key role in gene expression, cell proliferation, differentiation, migration, and apoptosis regulation. Activated myofibroblasts form specialized focal adhesions with high amounts of integrins 5, 1, and 3. The angiotensin-converting enzymes and integrin 1 (ITGB1) cross the plasma membrane, and the angiotensin-converting enzymes are also found in soluble form in the plasma when they are shed from the cell membrane. There are three ways for viruses to connect with integrins on the cell surface. In the first scenario, the virion functions as an antagonist by binding without internalization or by initiating integrin-mediated pathways. The second paradigm involves binding that does not result in internalization but does result in the activation of integrin-mediated pathways. In this case, the virion takes on the role of agonist. Finally, internalization of the virus can lead to infection and viral replication¹⁷.

Cytokines induced inflammation in Covid-19

In SARS-CoV infection, immune effector cells release significant amounts of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IFN-I, IFN-II, IL-1, IL-6, IL-12, IL-18, IL-33, TNF- α ,

TGF, and chemokines such as CCL2, CCL3, CCL5, CXCL8, CXCL9, and CXCL10, culminating in a lethal uncontrolled inflammatory response¹⁸. COVID-19 patients have varying levels of cytokines and chemokines as the disease progresses from mild to severe. Initial plasma levels of IL-1, IL-1ra, IL-7, IL-8, IL-10, IFN-, monocyte chemoattractant peptide (MCP)-1, macrophage inflammatory protein (MIP)-1A, MIP-1B, granulocyte colony stimulating factor (G-CSF), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) are increased in SARS-CoV-2-infected patients, according to a retrospective analysis¹⁹. Further research revealed that ICU patients have greater plasma concentrations of IL-2, IL-7, IL-17, IL-10, MCP1, MIP-1A, and TNF- α than non-ICU patients¹⁵. Furthermore, in severe infection, plasma levels of IL-2, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, and TNF- α are much higher than in non-severe illness^{20,21}. Plasma levels of IL-6, a cytokine thought to play a role in macrophage activation syndrome (MAS), rise in both moderate and severe COVID-19 patient groups²². Furthermore, the vast area of lung injury (50%) is closely connected with elevated levels of IL-6 and the subgroup of lymphocytes in peripheral blood, according to an assessment of pulmonary infiltration in patients with ARDS²³.

Long term effect of Covid-19

COVID-19 patients with and without prior neurologic disorders experience neurologic symptoms²⁴. After COVID-19 infection, neuropsychiatric disorders are more common than respiratory infections or flu. Within 6 months of infection, 34% of patients are diagnosed with a neurological disease, 2.1% have a stroke, 0.6% percent have brain hemorrhage, and 0.7% experience confusion²⁵. When compared to other health events such as elevated heart rate, influenza, other respiratory tract infections, skin infection, cholelithiasis, urolithiasis, and fracture of a large bone in patients with no prior psychiatric history, diagnosis of COVID-19 was associated with an increased incidence of a first psychiatric diagnosis in the following 14–90 days. During that period, 18% of COVID-19 patients are diagnosed with a mental health disorder, 58% of whom had no prior diagnosis. In adults over 65 years old, the incidence of a first diagnosis of dementia in the 14–90 days following a COVID-19 diagnosis was 16%²⁶.

Severity of COVID-19 disease is linked to a mutation in the SARS-CoV-2 virus

In cultured immortalized cells and primary human airway epithelial cells, the new G614 mutant virus replicates more efficiently than the ancestral D614 (Wuhan-HU-1/2019) virus, while in hamsters, the G614 mutant virus (B117 variant) replicates to higher titers in nasal-wash samples than the D614 variant²⁷. The G614 strain has a reproduction rate 31% higher than the D614 strain²⁸. In September 2020, B117 infections were discovered in the United Kingdom. The B117 lineage

includes a substantial number of genetic mutations in the spike protein²⁹. Other mutations in the spike protein P681H include a 69/70 deletion with a conformational change near the S1/S2 furin cleavage site with a mutation in ORF8 and a 69/70 deletion with a conformational change in the spike protein P681H near the S1/S2 furin cleavage site with a mutation in ORF8.

The B.1.351 lineage (20H/501Y.V2) variant has various mutations in the spike protein, including K417T, E484K, and N501Y, and lacks the deletion at 69/70. The

Figure 3. Diagrammatic representation of reported SARS-Cov2 variants following mutation from Wuhan SARS-Cov2 (D614).

human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor may bind more strongly to this variation, which was initially discovered in South Africa. The P.1 lineage (also known as 20J/501Y.V3) variant has 17 unique amino acid alterations and three deletions in the spike protein receptor-binding domain: K417T, E484K, and N501Y. It was initially discovered in Japan (Figure 3). Details of these mutations were recently published on the CDC's website at <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/more/scientific-brief-emerging-variant.html>. The BNT162b2 mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccine showed comparable neutralizing titers to the spike N501Y substitution³⁰; nevertheless, its effect on patients afflicted with B117 and N501Y variations remains to be validated.

The mutant strain more contagious and spread via air.

In hamsters, the mutant strain was more likely to spread through the air from one cage to another, showing that the G strain virus is more infectious. Once detected in the UK, it spread quickly throughout Europe, Asia, and the United States. The D strain is still present, although it only accounts for roughly 2% of all infections worldwide. The concern now is whether the G strain can evolve resistance to the newly discovered protein used to combat D strain immunizations. However, as immunity develops, it is possible that the new strain will be forced to evolve. Evolution favors viruses that can evade antibodies as time passes and more people develop immunity.

New G strain of virus may change the host.

The chance that the new variant could spread to one of the world's 1,400 bat species is a source of concern. Bats are good hosts for coronaviruses and are still considered the most likely source of SARS-CoV-2. Currently, investigators are concerned that if the virus's antigenic structure changes, the produced antibodies will no longer identify it. However, it is possible that this new virus will evolve into a common cold virus. After penetrating the lower respiratory system and beyond,

vaccine- and infection-induced immunity will most likely protect people from this new strain of virus. It would then join the four common coronaviruses that are currently circulating among the population and cause colds.

Double/Triple mutant

Cases of the B.1.617 strain have surged dramatically in India since the beginning of 2021. This virus, dubbed the "double mutant virus," has two important alterations: E484Q and L452R. B.1.617 has a number of mutations: G142D and E154K in the N-terminal antigenic supersite, L452R and E484Q in the receptor binding domain within the polybasic furin cleavage site at the S1/S2 boundary (P681R), 1 variant of the spike protein, including G142D and E154K in the N-terminal antigenic supersite, L452R and E484Q in the receptor binding domain within the polybasic furin cleavage site at the S1³¹. A "triple mutant variation" is created when three virus mutations combine to form a new variant. E154K, P681R, and Q1071H are some of the mutations found in the triple variation (B.1.618) newly discovered in West Bengal, India. E484K, a significant immune-escape mutation with two deletions in its spike protein, H146del and Y145del, characterizes the B.1.618 strain³². In addition to the usual symptoms of sore throat, body ache, fever, and loss of smell and taste, symptoms of the novel coronavirus triple-mutant variant include diarrhea, abdominal discomfort, rashes, conjunctivitis, confusion, and bleeding from the nose and throat. Mucormycosis (black fungus), an uncommon, life-threatening fungal infection caused by *Rhizopus arrhizus*, is associated with a variety of clinical disorders³³. Recent reports of black fungus infection in COVID-infected patients in India may be due to unsanitary conditions and contaminated equipment.

Types of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines

The challenge of developing and implementing large-scale vaccine production is rapidly increasing around the world. It requires a series of coordinating activities that must be organized in parallel but should be useful for decades with proper preclinical testing, phased clinical trials, planned production, and distribution. The immune system and implications for protective immunity may be good targets for vaccines. Vaccines that have been approved or are currently under development are divided into six categories (Table 1-5).

Inactivated Virus Vaccines

These vaccines are often created by exposing a virulent virus to a physical or chemical substance that DNA-based Vaccines and stages of development preserves the virus's immunogenicity while also acting as an immunogen (Table 2).

Virus-like particles (VLPs)

Virus-like particles (VLPs) are multiprotein structures that lack a viral genome but are co-expressed as non-infectious particles as a vaccine immunogen, sometimes yielding a safer vaccine option.

Developer / Researcher	Stage of Development	Product Description
Zyklus Cadila Healthcare Limited	Phase III	DNA; (ZyCoV-D) plasmid vaccine
Inovio Pharmaceuticals/ Beijing Advaccine Biotechnology/ VGXI Inc./ Richter-Helm Biologics/ Ology Bioservices/ International Vaccine Institute/ Seoul National University Hospital/ Thermo Fisher Scientific/ Kaneka Eurogentec	Phase II/III	DNA; (INO-4800) plasmid vaccine with electroporation ⁵⁰
Osaka University/ AnGes/ Takara Bio/ Cytiva/ Brickell Biotech	Phase II/III	DNA; (AG0301 & AG0302) plasmid vaccine + adjuvant
GeneOne and Life Science	Phase I/II	DNA; (GLS-5310)
Genexine Consortium (GenNBio, International Vaccine Institute, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST), Pohang University of Science and Technology (POSTECH)/ Blnex/ PT Kalbe Pharma	Phase I/II	DNA; (formerly GX-19) (GX-19N)
OncoSec Medical Incorporated / Providence Cancer Institute	Phase I	(CORVax12), IL-12 expression platform + "S" glycoprotein
SynVivo	Phase I	DNA; bsc-TRI-Spike
BioNet Asia/ Technovial/ Vax4COVID/ The University of Sydney/ The University of Western Australia/ Teleton Kids Institute/ PharmaJet	Pre-clinical	DNA; (COVIGEN) needle-free delivery
Chula Vaccine Research Center	Pre-clinical	DNA with electroporation
Ege University Drug Development and Pharmacokinetic Research Application Center (ARGEFAR)/ Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK)	Pre-clinical	DNA
Entos Pharmaceuticals/ Cytiva	Pre-clinical	DNA; (Covigenix)
Globe Biotech Limited, Bangladesh	Pre-clinical	DNA plasmid vaccine
Immunomic Therapeutics/ EpiVax/ PharmaJet	Pre-clinical	DNA; plasmid vaccine, needle-free delivery
Mediphage Biocell/ University of Waterloo/ Lambton College	Pre-clinical	DNA; msDNA-VLP
National Research Centre, Egypt	Pre-clinical	DNA; plasmid vaccine S, S1, S2, RBD & N
National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia	Pre-clinical	Plasmid DNA, nanostructured RBD
OPENCORONA Project: Karolinska Institute/ Justus Liebig University Gießen/ Public Health Agency of Sweden (FoHM)/ IGEA/ Cobra Biologics/ Adlego Biomedical/ Region Stockholm	Pre-clinical	DNA with electroporation
Scancell/ University of Nottingham/ Nottingham Trent University	Pre-clinical	DNA; plasmid vaccine RBD&N
Statens Serum Institute, Denmark	Pre-clinical	DNA; (CoVAXIX) plasmid vaccine
Takis/ Applied DNA Sciences/ Evviva/ Rottapharm Biotech	Pre-clinical	DNA; (COVID-eVax)
University of Cambridge/ DIOSynVax/ PharmaJet	Pre-clinical	DNA; (DIOS-CoVax2) synthetic gene inserts compatible with multiple delivery systems

Table 1. DNA-based Vaccines and stages of development Protein subunit vaccines

Vaccines made in vitro from bacteria, yeast, or mammalian cells and containing only important viral proteins or peptides (Table 3).

Developer / Researcher	Stage of Development	Product Description
Beijing Institute of Biological Products/ Sinopharm	Phase III	Inactivated, (BBIBP-CoV)51
Bharat Biotech/ Indian Council of Medical Research/ National Institute of Virology/ Ocugen/ Precisa Medicamentos	Phase III	Inactivated; whole virion (COVAXIN) (BBV152) ^{52, 53, 54}
Institute of Medical Biology, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences	Phase III	Inactivated ⁵⁵
Research Institute for Biological Safety Problems, Republic of Kazakhstan	Phase III	Inactivated, (QazCovid-in®)
Sinovac/ Instituto Butantan/ Bio Farma	Phase III	Inactivated (inactivated + alum); CoronaVac (formerly PiCoVacc) ^{52, 56, 57}
Wuhan Institute of Biological Products/ Sinopharm	Phase III	Inactivated ⁵⁸
Eredivis University	Phase II	Inactivated; (EBUCOV-VAC)
Shenzhen Kangtai Biological Products Co., Ltd./ Beijing Minhai Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	Phase II	Inactivated SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (Vero cell)
Valneva/ Dynavax/ National Institute for Health Research, United Kingdom	Phase I/II	Inactivated (Inactivated + CpG 1018), VLA2001
Shifa Pharmed Industrial Co	Phase I	COVID-19 inactivated vaccine (COVIRan Berekat)
Government Pharmaceutical Organization (GPO; Thailand) / Dynavax / PATH	Pre-clinical	Egg-based, inactivated, whole chimeric Newcastle Disease Virus (NDV) expressing membrane-anchored pre-fusion-stabilized trimeric SARS-CoV-2 S protein (Hexapro + CpG 1018)
Instituto Butantan (Brazil)/ Dynavax / PATH	Pre-clinical	
Institute of Vaccines and Medical Biologicals (IVAC; Vietnam) / Dynavax / PATH	Pre-clinical	
KM Biologics	Pre-clinical	Inactivated (inactivated + alum)
Kocaeli Farma Ilac ve Kimya San. A.S.	Pre-clinical	Inactivated
National Research Centre, Egypt	Pre-clinical	Inactivated whole virus
Osaka University/ BIKEN/ NIBIOHN	Pre-clinical	Inactivated
Selcuk University	Pre-clinical	Inactivated
Sinovac/ Dynavax	Pre-clinical	Inactivated + adjuvant (CpG 1018)
Codagenix / Serum Institute of India	Phase I	Live attenuated virus Vaccines and stages of development Single-dose, intramuscular, live attenuated vaccine, (COVL-VAC)
Indian Immunologicals Ltd/ Griffith University	Pre-clinical	Codon deoptimized live attenuated virus
Mehmet Ali Aydinlar University/ Acibadem Labmed Health Services A.S.	Pre-clinical	Codon deoptimized live attenuated vaccines
Meissa Vaccines	Pre-clinical	MV-014-210

Table 2. Inactivated/ Live attenuated virus Vaccines and stages of development

Virus- vectored vaccines

Viral vector-based vaccines are the vaccines

without antigens, but they use the body's cells to produce them. These antigen (s) are produced by transduced host cells after immunization.

DNA and mRNA vaccines

Viral antigens are encoded by a recombinant DNA plasmid and generated in host cells via a sequential transcription-to-translation process in DNA vaccines. mRNA vaccines, on the other hand, are produced in vitro and create viral antigens in the cytoplasm through direct protein translation in vivo (Table 1, 4).

Developer / Researcher	Stage of Development	Product Description
Medicago Inc.	Phase II/III	VLP: plant derived VLP adjuvanted with GSK or Dynavax adjuvants; (CoVLP) ⁶⁵
Serum Institute of India/ Accelagen Pty/ SpyBiotech	Phase I/II	RBD SARS-CoV-2 HBsAg VLP vaccine
Arizona State University	Pre-clinical	Myxoma virus co-expressing S, M, N and E proteins
Arizona State University	Pre-clinical	Plasmid driven production of virus like particles (VLPs) containing S, M, N and E proteins of SARS-CoV-2
ARTES Biotechnology	Pre-clinical	VLP; eVLP
Bezmialem Vakif University	Pre-clinical	VLP
Doherty Institute	Pre-clinical	VLP; unknown
Icosavax	Pre-clinical	VLP displaying the SARS-CoV-2 receptor-binding domain (RBD); (IVX-411)
Imophoron Ltd / Bristol University's Max Planck Centre	Pre-clinical	VLP; ADDomerTM multiepitope display
IrsiCaixa AIDS Research/ IRTA-CReSA/ Barcelona Supercomputing Centre/ Grifols	Pre-clinical	S protein integrated in HIV VLPs
Mahidol University/ The Government Pharmaceutical Organization (GPO)/ Siriraj Hospital	Pre-clinical	VLP + Adjuvant
Max-Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems	Pre-clinical	VLP
Medicago Inc./ GSK	Pre-clinical	VLP (CoVLP)+ Adjuvant
Medicago Inc./ Dynavax	Pre-clinical	VLP (CoVLP)+ Adjuvant (CpG 1018)
Middle East Technical University	Pre-clinical	VLP
Navarrabiomed, Oncoimmunology group	Pre-clinical	Virus-like particles, lentivirus, and baculovirus vehicles
OSIVAX	Pre-clinical	VLP (COVID-19 and SARS1)
Saiba GmbH	Pre-clinical	VLP; virus-like particle, based on RBD displayed on virus-like particle
Tampere University	Pre-clinical	VLPs produced in BEVS
University of Manitoba	Pre-clinical	Virus-like particle-based dendritic cell-targeting vaccine
University of Sao Paulo	Pre-clinical	VLPs peptides/whole virus
VBI Vaccines / National Research Council of Canada/ Therapure Biomanufacturing	Pre-clinical	Enveloped virus-like particle (eVLP): Pan-coronavirus vaccine candidate, targeting COVID-19, SARS, and MERS, spike protein (VBI-2900)

Table 3. Viral like particle Vaccines and stages of development

Live- attenuated virus vaccines

In this case, the virus is suppressed through in vitro or in vivo passage and genetic mutagenesis. By simulating live virus infection, the resultant virus becomes non-pathogenic or weakly pathogenic while retaining immunogenicity (Table 2).

Vaccines and treatments for COVID-19

Developer / Researcher	Stage of Development	Product Description
BioNTech/ Pfizer/ Fosun Pharma/ Rentschler Biopharma	Authorized	3 LNP-mRNAs; BNT162-9; 06-01-02
Moderna/ National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID)/ Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority (BARDA)/ Lonza/ Catalent/ Roviv/ Medidata/ BIOQUAL/ Baxter BioPharma Solutions	Authorized	RNA; LNP-encapsulated mRNA (mRNA 1273), (TAK-919) ^{61,64}
CureVac/Bayer/Novartis	Phase III	RNA; mRNA (CVnCoV)
Arcturus/Duke-NUS/ Catalent	Phase I/II	RNA; mRNA; (LUNAR-COV19)
Imperial College London/ VacEquity Global Health	Phase I/II	RNA; mRNA; LNP-mCoVsaRNA
People's Liberation Army (PLA) Academy of Military Sciences/ Walvax Biotech	Phase I	mRNA (ARCoV)
Providence Therapeutics Holdings Inc.	Phase 1	PTX-COVID19-B vaccine
BIOCAD	Pre-clinical	RNA; liposome-encapsulated mRNA
CanSino Biologics/Precision Nanosystems	Pre-clinical	RNA; mRNA lipid nanoparticle (mRNA-LNP)
Centro Nacional Biotecnologia (CNB-CSIC), Spain	Pre-clinical	RNA; Replicating defective SARS-CoV-2 derived RNAs
Chimeron Bio/ George Mason University's National Center for Biodefense and Infectious Disease	Pre-clinical	Self-amplifying RNA, self-assembling delivery system
China CDC / Tongji University / Stermia	Pre-clinical	RNA; mRNA
Chula Vaccine Research Center/University of Pennsylvania	Pre-clinical	LNP-mRNA; (ChulaCov19)
Curevac/GSK	Pre-clinical	Next-generation multi-valent mRNA-based vaccines
CureVac/UK Government (Vaccines Taskforce)	Pre-clinical	Multiple mRNA vaccine candidates against SARS-CoV-2 variants
Daiichi-Sankyo/ University of Tokyo's Institute of Medical Science	Pre-clinical	RNA; mRNA (DS-5670)
Eliskogen Therapeutics/ Fujita Health University	Pre-clinical	srRNA (EXG-5003)
Federal Budgetary Research Institution (FBRI) State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology "VECTOR"	Pre-clinical	RNA; mRNA
Fudan University / Shanghai JiaoTong University / RNACure Biopharma	Pre-clinical	RNA; LNP-encapsulated mRNA cocktail encoding VLP
Fudan University / Shanghai JiaoTong University / RNACure Biopharma	Pre-clinical	RNA; LNP-encapsulated mRNA cocktail encoding RBD
GeneOne Life Science / Houston Methodist	Pre-clinical	mRNA; (GLS-3000)
Genovva	Pre-clinical	Self-amplifying RNA
Globe Biotech Limited, Bangladesh	Pre-clinical	D614G variant LNP-encapsulated mRNA; (Bangavax)
Greenlight Biosciences	Pre-clinical	mRNA
IDAPAS- Hospital Clinic, Spain	Pre-clinical	mRNA
Infectious Disease Research Institute/ Amvris, Inc.	Pre-clinical	saRNA formulated in a NLC
Max-Planck Institute of Colloids and Interfaces	Pre-clinical	LNP-encapsulated mRNA encoding S
RNA immune, Inc.	Pre-clinical	RNA; several mRNA candidates
Sanofi Pasteur/ Translate Bio	Pre-clinical	LNP-mRNA

Table 4. RNA based Vaccines and stages of development

For effective treatment of COVID-19 and related disease, numerous treatment methods are available, and others are being tested in clinical trials. Depending on the severity of the disease and other medical conditions, bamlanivimab, casirivimab plus imdevimab, remdesivir, and dexamethasone with or without remdesivir may be used³⁴. Antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 may be present in the plasma of recovered COVID-19 patients, which could help fight the virus and its inflammatory response, but the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 convalescent plasma in pregnant and pediatric patients has not yet been determined³⁵. Mesenchymal stem cells are also being studied extensively as a therapeutic approach for COVID-19 patients with lung infection and inflammation³⁶. Interleukins play a vital role in the cytokine storm common in severe COVID-19, and interleukin inhibitors such as anakinra (which inhibits IL-1), sarilumab, tocilizumab (which inhibits IL-6), and interferons are being studied³⁷. Alternatives to dexamethasone include prednisone, methylprednisolone, and hydrocortisone, all of which may help prevent SARS-CoV-2-induced systemic inflammation, lung damage, and multisystem organ dysfunction³⁸. Vitamins C, D, and zinc are also indicated for COVID-19 patients who are not critically ill, although their exact role has yet to be determined³⁹. With the goal of developing a safe and effective vaccine for COVID-19, researchers are looking into DNA-based and RNA-based techniques as well as replicating and nonreplicating vector strategies. SARS-CoV-2 vaccines based on mRNA are currently licensed. Antibodies or immune cells bind to molecules on the virus's surface to provide immunity. If alterations in these components on the virus's surface occur, antibodies will be unable to bind to them as strongly, allowing the virus to escape, which is why the seasonal flu vaccine needs to be

Developer / Researcher	Stage of Development	Product Description
Anhui Zhifei Longcom Biopharmaceutical/ Institute of Microbiology, Chinese Academy of Sciences	Phase III	Adjuvanted recombinant protein (RBD-Dimer). (ZF2001)
Instituto Finlay de Vacunas	Phase III	rRBD produced in CHO-cell chemically conjugate to tetanus toxoid; (FINLAY-FR-2) (SOBERANA 02)
Novavax/Emergent Biosolutions/ Praha Vaccines/ Biofabri/ Fujifilm Diosynth Biotechnologies/ FDB/ Serum Institute of India/ SK bioscience/ Takeda Pharmaceutical Company Limited/ AGC Biologics/ PolyPeptide Group/ Endo	Phase III	Protein subunit; Full length recombinant SARS CoV-2 glycoprotein nanoparticle vaccine adjuvanted with Matrix M; (NVX-CoV2373) (SARS-CoV-2 rS)
Medigen Vaccine Biologics Corp/ NIAID/ Dynavax	Phase II	MVC-CoV1901 vaccine injection; S-2 P protein + CpG 1018
Sanofi Pasteur/ GSK	Phase II	Protein subunit; S protein, baculovirus production
West China Hospital, Sichuan University	Phase II	RBD (baculovirus expressed in Sf9 cells)
Biological E Ltd/ Dynavax/ Baylor College of Medicine	Phase I/II	Protein subunit; (BECCOV2)
Center for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (CIGB), Havana	Phase I/II	CIGB-669 (RBD-AgnHB)
Federal Budgetary Research Institution (FBR) State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology "VECTOR"	Phase I/II	Peptide vaccine, EpiVacCorona
Instituto Finlay de Vacunas	Phase I/II	RBD + Adjuvant (FINLAY-FR-1) (SOBERANA 01)
Nanogen Pharmaceutical Biotechnology	Phase I/II	Recombinant SARS-CoV-2 spike protein, aluminum adjuvanted
Shinogi & Co., Ltd/ National Institute of Infectious Disease, Japan	Phase I/II	Recombinant protein vaccine S-268019, baculovirus expression
VIDO-InterVac, University of Saskatchewan	Phase I/II	Protein subunit, adjuvanted microsphere peptide, (COVAC-1 & COVAC-2)
Adimmune Corporation	Phase I	Baculovirus-insect cells expression system, spike (S) protein (tAdimrSC-2D)
Center for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (CIGB), Havana	Phase I	CIGB-66 (RBD + aluminum hydroxide)
Clover Biopharmaceuticals Inc./ Dynavax	Phase I	Protein subunit, native like trimeric subunit spike protein; (SCB-2019)
Covavax/ University of Nebraska Medical Center (UNMC)/ DASA/ United Biomedical Inc. Asia	Phase I	S1-RBD-protein; Multipeptide-Based Vaccine (MVP); UB-612
Razi Vaccine and Serum Research Institute	Phase I	SARS-CoV-2 recombinant Spike protein vaccine (Razi Cov Pars)
University Hospital Tuebingen	Phase I	SARS-CoV-2 HLA-DR peptides, (CoVAC-1)
Vaccine Pty Ltd/ Flinders University/ Oracle/ Medytox/ Sypharma/ Oxford Expression Technologies	Phase I	Protein subunit; recombinant spike protein with AdVax adjuvant (COVAX-19)

Table 5. Protein based sub-unit Vaccines and stages of development

updated every year. If this occurs, a COVID vaccine would need to be updated on a regular basis. There are over 200 COVID vaccine candidates in various phases of research but is too early to know how many have evolution-proof characteristics. The vaccine from AstraZeneca has been linked to significant and occasionally fatal blood clots in rare situations⁴⁰. Patients who experienced clots after vaccination had antibodies that activated their platelets, and younger people appear to be more susceptible than older people. Vaccines that only provide temporary relief put patients at risk and may also render other vaccines ineffective if viruses evolve that are resistant to many vaccines at the same time.

Vaccine efficacy by coronavirus variant

The first significant change in SARS-CoV-2 occurred early in the pandemic, in March and April 2020, when the original strain was replaced globally by a new variant known as D614G⁴¹. The important mutation in this variant, which is found in the S protein, has been proven to improve the virus's replication efficiency and transmissibility⁴². Although neutralizing antibodies (NAbs) did not recognize this variant, it served as a warning. Another variant began to spread in August 2020 in the United Kingdom (where such events are closely monitored), and infections in that country climbed substantially from November 2020 to January 2021. This variant has now been identified in several countries, including the USA. The first variant "UK strain," known as B.1.1.7. N501Y, contains a critical sequence alteration in the S protein that appears to boost the transmissibility of SARS-CoV-2, but in a somewhat different way than D614G. Fortunately, the

site of the N501Y alteration renders it unlikely to influence most of the NAb binding sites on the receptor-binding domain (RBD) in terms of vaccine protection. Another new variant, N501Y.V2 (or B.1.351), has been discovered in South Africa, Japan, and Brazil (P.1) with similar infectious properties. The N501Y.V2 strain causes more sequence changes than both the D614G and the B.1.1.7 variants, and these changes are more worrying because they are located inside or close to the RBD⁴³. Recently, India reported a variant B.1.617.2 which spreads more easily, with transmission rates 30–100% higher than the other reported variants in the UK, South Africa, or Brazil. Most recently, the US identified two variants in California, B1.427 and B1.429, that reduce the effectiveness of antibodies generated by COVID-19 infection or by vaccines (Table 6). Since these variant identification numbers can cause confusion, the World Health Organization (WHO) simplified them: The UK variant B.1.117 is known as Alpha, South African variant B1.351 is Beta, the Brazil variant P.1 is gamma, and the Indian variant B1.617.2 is Delta. According to the WHO, more than 4,500 sequences of variants from more than 40 countries have been uploaded to a coronavirus database and could be less. However, many countries, including India, are sequencing only a fraction of their virus cases, so it is difficult to determine just how large a role the variant is playing in surges. Recent reports indicate that inactivated vaccines, such as those developed in China, seem to induce lower effective, as currently reported in cases in Seychelles. It is too early to know how replication-default vaccines (Johnson & Johnson, Janssen, AstraZeneca), or adjuvant purified protein vaccines (Novavax and Sanofi- NAb levels GSK) may be affected by simian or human adenovirus vaccine replication defeat. Researchers across the world are currently working to better understand how N501Y.V2 an related variants

Antibody Name	Source	Neutralizing activity	Neutralizing mechanism	Reference
S230.15 and m396	Human	Neutralize human and palm civet SARS-CoV	Recognize epitopes (residues 408, 442, 443, 460, 475) on SARS-CoV S1 protein, interfering with RBD-ACE2 receptor interaction	66
S109.85 227, 14S230.15	Human	Neutralize human (Urbani, GZ02, CUHK-W1), palm civet (HC/SZ/61/03), and raccoon dog(A031G) SARS-CoV infectious clones containing 5 variants	Inhibit the binding of SARS-CoV RBD-ACE2 receptor	67
80RscFv	Human	Neutralize live SARS-CoV (strain Urbani) infection	Epitopes on SARS-CoV S1 (residues 261–672), blocking RBD-ACE2 binding and inhibiting syncytium formation	68
CR3022 CR3014 scFv	Human	Neutralize live SARS-CoV (strain HKU-39849) infection; CR3022 could neutralize CR3014 escape variants	Recognize epitopes on SARS-CoV RBD (residues 318–510); CR3022 binds SARS-CoV-2 RBD with high affinity	69, 70
Tocilizumab and Sarilumab	Recombinant humanized monoclonal antibody	IL-6 receptor antagonists	Targeting IL-6 and its receptor (IL6R) by tocilizumab and siltuximab monoclonal antibodies could mitigate cytokine storm	71
Bevacizumab	Recombinant humanized monoclonal antibody	VEGF inhibitor	Target vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), inhibit it and prevents acute lung injury (ALI) and ARDS	72

Table 6. Neutralizing antibodies for Covid-19.

affect these vaccines. In addition to avoiding immunity

recognition due to vaccine, variants are also less susceptible to monoclonal antibody (nMAb) neutralization. For instance, changes to N501Y in the B.1.1.7 variant almost eliminate the activity of several nMAbs, and a study by a South African team shows that almost all the nMAbs tested against N501Y.V2 are no

Vaccine	Efficacy at preventing disease: D614G & B.1.1.7	Efficacy at preventing infection: D614G & B.1.1.7	Efficacy at preventing disease: B.1.351, P.1, B.1.617	Efficacy at preventing infection: B.1.351, P.1, B.1.617
Pfizer/BioNTech	91%	86%	86%	82%
Moderna	94%	89%	89%	85%
AstraZeneca	74%	52%	35%	31%
Johnson & Johnson (Janssen)	72%	72%	64%	57%
Sputnik-V	92%	81%	59%	52%
Novavax	89%	79%	49%	43%
CoronaVac	50%	44%	32%	28%
Sinopharm	73%	65%	47%	41%
Tianjin CanSino	66%	58%	42%	37%
Covaxin	78%	69%	50%	44%
Other mRNA vaccines	91%	86%	86%	82%
All other vaccines	75%	66%	57%	50%

Table 7. Efficacy of vaccines in response to coronavirus variants.

longer effective, but recently two new variants like delta plus and Lamda is identified in several countries including UK that accounts for 82% of new infections and still not sure that current vaccinated population is completely protected with this new variants⁴⁴. The efficacy of the top 10 vaccines has been shown in the Table 7.

Do the New SARS-CoV-2 Variants Affect Vaccine Efficacy?

So far, the new variants tend to affect COVID-19's potential to spread but have no effect on how sick people get from the virus, and currently available vaccines appear to be effective against the novel mutations. Vaccines are designed to produce a wide range of antibodies to multiple portions of the virus, so that even if one portion of the virus mutates, the antibodies will still identify another. It is likely that a variant will emerge that diminishes vaccine efficacy, and manufacturers are working to develop new vaccines that will protect against new SARS-CoV-2 strains.

Efficacy of the vaccines

Numerous vaccines are being developed, but only few are showing good results in clinical trials. The clinical trials of Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna vaccines

showed 95% and 94.1% efficacy, respectively, whereas the Johnson & Johnson vaccine, which was tested in the United States, Brazil, and South Africa, had 66% efficacy

Vaccine efficacy by coronavirus variant

The first significant change in SARS-CoV-2 occurred early in the pandemic, in March and April 2020, when

overall and 85% efficacy against severe disease^{45,46}.

Pfizer-BioNTech

This is an mRNA vaccine that codes for the virus's spike protein and is encapsulated in a lipid nanoparticle. Once injected, the cells churn out the spike protein, triggering the body's immune system to recognize the virus. It has demonstrated 95% efficacy.

Moderna

Messenger RNA (mRNA) is a highly unstable molecule that is used to create proteins in cells. mRNA can be synthesized in a laboratory and, when injected into cells, can cause pieces of proteins to be made. When these small pieces of protein (peptides) leave the cell, the body can develop an immune reaction to them. The Moderna vaccine is stable at 36–46° F and has an efficacy rate of 94.5%

Why two doses of Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna

The first dose helps to prime your immune system. It introduces it to the spike protein and allows it to generate a small immune response prior to the second dose. Time is needed to allow this process to develop properly⁴⁷.

Johnson & Johnson's Single-Dose COVID-19 Vaccine

This option uses a modified adenovirus (Ad26.COVS. S) to spur antibody production in its recipients. Overall efficacy was 66% but in the severe critical Covid-19 it showed an efficacy rate of 76% and in the variant studies (20H/501Y.V2), the vaccine efficacy was 52.0%.

NVX-CoV2373 Covid-19 Vaccine against the B.1.351 Variant

For this vaccine researchers used a baculovirus for the first time to insert into the gene for the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein into moth cells, which produced spikes on their cell membranes. They then harvested the spike proteins and mixed them with a synthetic soap-like particle (saponin) in which the spikes embed. The vaccine efficacy was 60.1% in the normal population⁴⁸.

Nasal Spray (Ab's) to Beat COVID-19 as a game changer

IgM has been engineered as a promising drug model with powerful neutralization, wide coverage of variants, with desirable pharmacokinetics and safety profiles. We intend that developed; IgM, administered could provide both for COVID-19 and other respiratory viral conditions as new therapeutic platform ⁴⁹.

Normal working life is affected due to Covid-19

The remote workers before the Covid-19 pandemic were less than 4% of the US workforce; however, after the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak, it shot up to 56% of the US. Approximately, 14 times increase within a single quarter. A remote work-study found that 86% took advantage of those who had the option to work remotely. A study indicated that even when offices can open back up, around one-third of professionals predict up to 75% of the workforce might go fully remote in the next 15 years. However, if the current vaccines work as well as hoped and the virus becomes the sniffles, still the situation of working style may not change.

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Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflicts of interest associated with the material presented in this paper.

Ethics Statement

This paper is a perspective, so it did not need ethical approval.

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